

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17337177

Impact Of Training Needs Analysis On Employee Performance: A Study Of Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto

¹Yusha'u Ahmad Rufa'i, ²Nuraddeen Muhammad Koko, PhD, ³Sa'idu Idris, PhD and ⁴Prof. Malami Muhammad Maishanu

¹Department of Public Administration, Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto, Nigeria,

^{2,3}Department of Public Administration, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria,

⁴Department of Business Administration, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the impact of training needs analysis on employee performance of Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto. The study used close-ended questionnaires to obtain information from the respondents. A survey research design was employed. The paper had a sample of 210 respondents from the 477 Non-academic staff of the Polytechnic. The sample size was drawn using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) population and sample size Determination. A total of 179 valid responses formed the basis of analysis. The findings reveal a positive impact between training needs analysis and employee performance. The study concludes that training needs analysis is essential for enhancing employee performance and achieving organizational goals. The paper recommends that, the management should establish a structured and periodic Training Needs Analysis process to ensure training programmes are aligned with evolving job requirements and employee skill gaps. Regular TNAs will help identify current performance gaps and tailor training interventions to specific departmental or individual needs, improving employee effectiveness and organisational efficiency. Similarly, the need for the management to develop a comprehensive and strategic training roadmap, prioritizing areas that directly impact performance outcome. This ensures that resources are allocated efficiently, and training efforts are focused on high-impact competencies that can enhance service delivery and institutional performance.

Keywords: Training, Training Needs Analysis, Employee Performance

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly dynamic and competitive work environment, organisations especially educational institutions, must continuously seek ways to improve employee performance and institutional productivity. One key strategy to achieving this is through the implementation of effective training programmes. However, the success of any training initiative largely depends on how well it is aligned with the actual needs of the employees and the organization. This alignment is made possible through a structured process known as training needs analysis (Goldstein & Ford, 2002).

Training Needs Analysis (TNA) involves identifying performance gaps, analyzing job requirements, and determining the necessary skills, knowledge, and competencies required to bridge those gaps (Wognum, 2001). When properly conducted, TNA helps to ensure that training programmes are relevant, goal oriented, and capable of producing measurable improvements in employee productivity.

Moreover, empirical studies have demonstrated a significant relationship between well-conducted TNA and improved employee outcomes such as job satisfaction, productivity, and commitment (Al-Khayyat & Elgamal, 1997). In the context of the Nigerian Polytechnics, where resource constraints and administrative bottlenecks are common, understanding the impact of TNA on employee performance is crucial for informed decision making and policy formulation.

Training and development have been widely recognised as key strategies for enhancing employee competencies and achieving organizational objectives. However, the effectiveness of training programmes is often undermined when they are not preceded by a systematic assessment of actual training needs. In many public institutions, including tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria, training programmes are sometimes implemented haphazardly, without a clear understanding of the specific skill gaps they are meant to address. In Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto, there appears to be a dearth of empirical evidence to suggest that training interventions are consistently guided by a structured TNA. This raises concerns about the efficiency and effectiveness of such programmes in improving employee performance. When training is not aligned with the real needs of staff and the strategic goals of the institution, it may lead to poor resource utilization, employee dissatisfaction, and minimal improvement in job performance (Salas et al., 2012).

Furthermore, there is limited empirical studies that critically examine the relationship between TNA and employee performance within the context of the Nigerian Polytechnics. This research gap limits the ability of policymakers and administrators to design evidence-based training strategies that can yield measurable performance improvements. Therefore, this paper seeks to assess the impact of TNA on employee performance in Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto. By focusing on this institution, this paper contributes to a deeper understanding of how training strategies can be optimized through needs assessment, and how such practices can translate into tangible performance improvements in the public tertiary education sector. The concern of this paper is: To what extent does TNA impact on employee performance in Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto?

2. 1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Concept of Training

Training is a process for equipping the employees with specific skills for instance, technical skills like plumbing, electrical wiring, repairing, artistic skills, clerical and typing skills that would enable them to improve on their present performance and overall efficiency.

According to Salas et al. (2012), training is a continuous, dynamic, and technology-enabled process through which employees acquire and apply job relevant knowledge, skills, and behaviors in alignment with organizational goals. Noe (2020), sees training as the process of improving the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of employees to achieve higher job performance, adaptability, and engagement in dynamic work environments. Noe, emphasizes the strategic role of training in employee motivation, retention, and performance enhancement. Training in the digital era is an ongoing process of up skilling and reskilling employees through technology-enabled methods to respond to rapid changes in the workplace (World Economic Forum, 2020). This definition focuses on reskilling and agility, driven by automation and technological advancement.

Similarly, modern training is data-driven, personalized learning delivered through technology designed to meet individual learning needs and organizational goals in real time. This reflects the growing importance of AI-powered platforms and personalization in organizational learning system (Bersin, 2021). Training as a component of human capital development that systematically equips employees with competencies required to perform current and future roles (OECD, 2021). This highlights how training is a long-term investment in workforce competence and employability.

2.1.2 Concept of Training Needs Analysis

Training Needs Analysis (TNA) is a crucial process in human resource development that identifies the gap between current employee performance and the desired performance levels in order to determine

what training is necessary to bridge those gaps. Different scholars have proposed various frameworks and concepts for understanding and conducting TNA.

Thus, TNA as discussed by Armstrong (2014) is a systematic process aimed at identifying gaps between current and required performance in the workplace. TNA is essential for developing effective training programmes that align with organizational goals and employee development needs. He emphasizes that the core purpose of TNA is to determine whether training is the right solution to a performance problem and, if so, to define what training is needed, who needs it, and how it should be delivered.

According to a recent study by Liu et al. (2023), AI-driven TNA Tools can accurately predict skill gaps and recommend customized learning pathways, significantly improving training efficiency.

Similarly, Singh and Jain (2024) emphasize the role of continuous learning ecosystems where TNA is an ongoing, integrated process rather than a one-time assessment. Therefore, TNA remains a foundational element in strategic human resource development. Its modern iteration leverages technology and data to become more predictive and tailored, aligning individuals' growth with organizational success with evolving workplace dynamics and digital transformation, TNA must also evolve as continuous and dynamic process.

2.1.3 Review of Empirical Studies

Although several studies have examined the relationship between training initiatives and employee performance in various sectors of the Nigerian public service, there remains a noticeable gap in the contextual and methodological focus of existing literature, particularly with regards to TNA as a distinct and strategic component of human resource development.

Lloyd (2021), in a study on the Bayelsa State Civil Service on the impact of training on employee job performance, utilized a survey design to explore the relationship between training and employee job performance. Analysis of responses from 70 participants revealed that effective training, informed by needs assessments, significantly enhances employee performance, satisfaction, and job commitment. The study emphasized the importance of routine TNA and adequate budgeting to ensure that public sector training initiatives remain responsive to both individual and organizational objectives. Lloyd (2021) explored the impact of training on employee performance in Bayelsa State Civil Service, focusing primarily on general training interventions without isolating the diagnostic role of TNA in identifying relevant skill gaps. The study emphasised outcomes of training but did not address whether those training programmes were preceded by a structured needs analysis to ensure alignment with actual job requirements.

Similarly, Omolayo (2022) explored the effect of training and development on staff performance in the National Assembly, Abuja. While recognizing the presence of training programmes, the study noted disconnects between training initiatives and actual employee needs due to inadequate TNA practices. This misalignment often led to ineffective training outcomes. The study advocated for the integration of regular TNA to align training contents with organizational goals and performance and creating a conducive environment for applying acquired skills to improve employee performance.

Omolayo, (2022) studied the effect of training and development on staff performance in the National Assembly, Abuja. There is limited empirical evidence on whether systematic TNA influences employee performance within Nigerian tertiary educational institutions (Polytechnics). The study addresses the gap by investigating the impact of TNA on employee performance at Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto. Previous work focused on broader training provision in Federal legislative settings; however, the diagnostic stage of TNA and its quality critical for the effectiveness of subsequent training remains understudied in Polytechnic environment. The present quantitative study fills this gap.

Yusuf et al. (2023) conducted a study on the Adamawa State Ministry of Education, assessing the impact of training and development on employee performance. The study employed a descriptive qualitative design to assess how training need analysis and training method influence employee performance. The study highlighted that a significant proportion of performance variation ($R^2 = 0.89$) could be attributed to well-structured training programmes grounded in proper needs analysis. The study concluded that TNA is

instrumental in identifying and addressing workforce gaps, thereby improving service delivery in the public sector.

Yusuf et al. (2023), in their work on the impact of training and development in the Adamawa State Ministry of Education, provided valuable insights into sector specific training challenges. However, their study also generalized training as a developmental process, neglecting the systematic analysis phase of TNA that ensures the right competencies are targeted. Their research lacked a diagnostic lens and did not measure the extent to which training interventions addressed identified performance deficiencies.

Similarly, Anas (2024) examined the broader implications of training reforms on employee competencies in the Nigerian public sector. Utilising a structured questionnaire and analysing data from 672 respondents, the study found a strong positive correlation between training and key performance variables such as knowledge and skill acquisition. The study confirmed that the strategic implementation of TNA enhances the effectiveness of training programmes, thereby improving employee capacity and organizational performance. Nevertheless, the study concentrated on structural and policy reforms without investigating the foundational processes of TNA that precede reform execution. While the study addressed outcomes of reforms, it did not consider how initial training needs were identified or misidentified.

Collectively, these studies underscore the critical role of TNA in enhancing employee performance within public sector institutions. Therefore, institutions like Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto, could benefit significantly from systematically conducted training needs assessments to guide employee development initiatives. This study, therefore, addresses this gap by focusing explicitly on Training Need Analysis and its impact on employee performance in a polytechnic setting, using Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto, as area of study. It seeks to offer empirical insights into how systematic TNA processes impact on the relevance, effectiveness, and outcomes of training interventions in academic institutions.

2.1.4 Theoretical Framework

Several theories explain how organizations could use internal resources to attain competitive advantages, for example, Organization and Administrative Theory, Progressive Utilization Theory (PROUT), Ability Motivation Opportunity Theory (AMO) and Resource-based View (RBV). The organization and administrative theory concentrate on the legitimization of organisation exercises. While the PROUT emphasizes advances in monetary independence, cooperatives naturally adjust, and RBV clarifies a craft of using organizations' resources for competitive advantage. AMO also emphasizes certain reciprocal features about how HRM explains the relationship with performance (Paauwe, 2009).

However, this paper is underpinned by the Human Capital Theory, developed by Gary Becker (1964), who posits that individuals and organizations derive long-term economic benefits from investing in education and training. The theory views employees' skills, knowledge, and competencies as assets that increase productivity and efficiency. Therefore, the theory posits that investments in employee training lead to higher productivity and efficiency. While Gary Becker's Human Capital Theory has provided a useful framework for understanding the link between education, skills, and productivity, it has been criticised for being overly individualistic, economically reductionist, and blind to systematic and cultural factors. These criticisms have led to more nuanced theories in sociology, labour economics, and education studies. In this context, TNA serves as a strategic tool to identify performance gaps and areas where training can enhance skills. By aligning training with actual needs, public sector organizations ensure efficient use of resources and maximize the return on training and employee performance.

3.1 METHODOLOGY

The research design used for this paper is descriptive survey approach. The descriptive survey research is best suited to measure the degree of association or impact between two or more variables without manipulating them. That is TNA can be operationalised into measurable components (e.g., identification of skill gaps, employee feedback, task analysis), while Employee Performance can be quantified (e.g.,

KPIs, appraisal records, self-assessment, or supervisor ratings). This descriptive design helps to assess the impact and relationship between TNA and employee performance in a real-world institutional context. Based on the population of Non-academic staff from the record of the Umaru Ali Shinkafi polytechnic, Sokoto (477), the paper identified a sample size of 210 employees using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) population and sample size Determination Table. Simple random sampling technique was used, which made it possible for each person to have an equal chance of being selected. The study used close-ended questionnaires to obtain information from the respondents as survey research, and the data analysis was by frequency count to interpret the data. Frequency and percentages was used since there are research questions of different responses and ideas. Out of the 210 questionnaires administered to respondents, 179 were filled correctly and returned. Therefore, the analysis was based on the 179 returned questionnaires. Hence, Regression analysis was used to test the formulated null hypothesis.

4.1 RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Table 1

Table 1 is the summary of demographic information of the respondents which are as follows
I. Gender, ii Age. iii. Qualification and Work experience

S/N	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage
1	Gender	Male	126	70.39
		Female	53	29.61
2	Age	18-25	15	8.4
		26-45	54	30.1
		46-55	76	42.5
		55 and above	34	19.00
3	Qualification	Primary Cert.	00	00.00
		SSCE	29	16.2
		Diploma	51	28.5
		BSc/HND	82	45.8
		Master Degree	17	9.5
4	Work experience	1-5 years	28	15.6
		6-10 years	67	37.4
		10 and above	84	47.00

Source: Field Work, 2025

Hypothesis: Training need analysis has no significant impact on employee performance in Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto.

Table 2:

Summary of the Regression statistics on the significant impact of training need analysis and employee performance of the Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto.

Path Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.320	.198		6.680	.000
	TRN	.610	.073	.520	8.313	.000

a. Dependent Variable: EMP

Table 3

Model Summary: Evaluation of R-square

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
EMP	.520 ^a	.271	.267	.75558

a. Predictors: (Constant), TRN

The coefficient statistics which evaluates how the regression explains the relative contributions of employee performance of Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto shows that the regression is statistically significant with a significant level of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significance, indicating that training needs contributes significantly in the employee performance of the Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto.

In Table 2 above, the constant value indicates that there can always be 0.610 contributions of employee performance of the Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto regardless of the change in training needs analysis. However, a change in training needs analysis will always generate 0.520 of employee performance provided other variables remain constant at a significance level of 0.000 as it is below 0.05 level of significance. This implies that TNA has a significant contribution on employee performance of the Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that TNA has no significant impact on employee performance of the Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto is hereby not accepted.

The results of regression statistics analysis in Table 3 present a positive correlation R-value of 0.520 which suggest a positive impact between TNA and employee performance of the Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto. The Table equally presents the R-square value of 0.271 which suggest that training needs analysis accounted for 27% contribution in employee performance, the remaining 73% is accounted for other variables like recruitment, selection, transfer, performance evaluation, etc.

5.1 CONCLUSION

The paper examined the impact of training needs analysis on employee performance of the Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto. The findings revealed that TNA plays a crucial role in enhancing employee performance. The paper found a positive and significant impact of TNA on employee performance, indicating that employees who undergo training and development programmes tend to perform better.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Institutionalize Regular Training Needs Assessments: The management should establish a structured and periodic TNA process to ensure training programmes are aligned with evolving job requirements and employee skills gaps. Regular TNAs will help identify current performance gaps and tailor training interventions to specific departmental or individual needs, improving employee effectiveness and organizational efficiency. Similarly, the need for the management to develop a comprehensive and strategic training roadmap, prioritizing areas that directly impact performance outcome. This ensures that resources are allocated efficiently, and training efforts are focused on high-impact competencies that can enhance service delivery and institutional performance.

REFERENCES

- Adewale, A. A. (2015). Manpower Development, Capacity building and service delivery in Ife-East Local Government Area, Osun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Public Administration and Policy Research*, 7(1), 1-10.
- Al-Khayyat, R. M., & Elgamal, M. A. (1997). Training needs assessment of managers in the ministry of social affairs and labour in the state of Kuwait: A model for the development of managerial competencies. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 21(2), 63–70.

- Anas, A. A. (2024). Investigating the effect of training reform on employee competencies in the Nigerian public sector. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 8(1), 175-183.
- Armstrong, M. (2014). *Human Resource Management Practice* (13th ed.). Kogan Page
- Barney, J., & Wright, P. (1998). On becoming a strategic partner. The role of human resources in gaining competitive advantage. *Human Resource Management*, 37(1), 31-46.
- Bersin, J. (2021). *Human resource predictions for 2021: A New World of Work*.
- Cooke, F. (2000). Human resource strategy to improve organizational performance: A route for British firms Working Paper No 9 EWERC. Manchester: School of Management.
- Debrah, Y., & Ofori, G. (2006). Human resource development of professionals in an emerging economy: The case of the Tanzanian Construction Industry. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 17(3), 440-463.
- Evans, J., & Lindsay, W. (1999). *The management and control of quality* (4th ed.). Ohio USA: South-Western College Publishing.
- Goldstein, I. L., & Ford, J. K. (2002). *Training in organizations: Needs assessment, development, and evaluation* (4th ed.). Belmont, CA: Wadsworth.
- Haslinda, A., & Mahyuddin, M.Y. (2009). The effectiveness of training in the public service, *American Journal of Scientific Research*, 6, 39-51.
- Isa, Y., Sunday, N. J., Adamu, A., & Solomon, L. (2023). Impact of training and development on employee performance in Adamawa State Ministry of Education, Yola. *Scholarly Journal of Social Sciences Research*, 2(8), 21-31.
- Ismael, A., & Bongogoh, S. (2007). The supervisor's role in training programmes: an empirical study in one city based local authority in Sarawak, Malaysia. *Unitar e-Journal* 3(2).
- Joseph, B. O. (2015). An Assessment of the Training and Developmental Needs of Employees in Nigerian Local Government. *Review of Public Administration and Management*, 3(1), 1-10.
- Joseph-Obi, C., & Arugu, O. N. (2019). The impact of workers training on the organizational performance of the staff of the Ministry of Labour and Productivity, Port Harcourt. *IFE Psycho Logia*, 27(2), 1-10.
- Liu, Y., Zhang, H., & Patel, R. (2023). AI driven training need analysis: Enhancing workforce capability through predictive learning. *International Journal of Training and Development*, 27(3), 212-229.
- Lloyd, J.E. (2021). The impact of training on employee job performance: A study of Bayelsa State Civil Service. *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research*, 6(2), 25-37
- Mullins, J., & Laurie, (2007). *Management and organizational behaviour* (8th ed.). Edinburg Prentice Hall: Pearson Education.
- Noe, R.A. (2020). *Employee training and development* (8th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Obi-Anike, H. O., & Ekwe, M. C. (2014). Impact of Training and Development on Organizational Effectiveness: Evidence from Selected Public Sector Organizations in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(29), 66-75.
- Omolayo, A.M. (2022). Effect of staff training and development on employee performance: A study of National Assembly, Abuja. Master's Thesis, National Institute for Legislative and Democratic Studies.
- Onuoha, S. N., & Njoku, A. C. (2023). Effect of staff training and development in relation to employee productivity in Aba North Local Government Council of Abia State. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 7(8), 158-169.
- Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (2021). Skills for jobs database.
- Salas, E., Tannenbaum, S.I., Kraiger, K., & Smith-Jentsch, K.A. (2012). The science of training and development in organizations: What matters in practice? *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 13(2), 74-101

- Singh, P., & Jain, M. (2024). Strategic training need analysis in the age of digital transformation. *Journal of organizational Learning and Development*, 15(1), 34-49
- Thomson, A. (2002). *Managing people and training and development* (3rd ed.). Butterworth: Heinemann
- Wasilu, S. (2013). A study of causes of poor attitude to work among workers of both public and private sector organization in Bauchi State-Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 3(7), 143-152.
- Wognum, A. A. M. (2001). Vertical integration of HRD policy within companies. *Human Resource Development International*, 4(3), 407-421.
- World Economic Forum. (2020). The Future of Jobs Report.
- Wright, P., McCormick, B., Sherman, W., & McMahan, G. (2003). The role of human resource practices in petro-chemical refinery performance. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 10(4), 551-571.
- Zayum, S. S., Aule, O., & Teslim, A. B. (2022). Training and employee productivity in the Benue State Ministry of Agriculture, Nigeria. *British Journal of Multidisciplinary and Advanced Studies*, 2(1), 1-10.